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Cold-pretreated seeds behave differently with different durations of exposure to cold temperatures. Under cold stress in both the laboratory and the field, the 1-d

pretreated seeds exhibited significantly higher root/shoot growth and emergence above soil compared with the control and other pretreated sets. This improved

seedling growth was associated with significantly higher protein synthesis ability during early hours (22-24 h) of germination under cold stress. ■

Crop and resource management

Fertilizer management

Potassium fertilizer for higher yields in scented rice

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The area under scented rice varieties is growing because of the premium price they command compared with that of high-yielding nonscented varieties. The fertilizer recommendation for nonscented varieties is high (150, 26.4, 49.8 kg NPK/ha) compared with scented varieties (60 kg N/ha and 13.2 kg P/ha for tall, and 90 kg N/ha and 13.2 kg P/ha for dwarf). High N fertilizer doses lead to lodging of scented rices, whereas K enhances the plant's resistance against lodging. Applying K is not recommended for these varieties.

We conducted a field study to compare the responses of three scented rices (HB1, HBC19, Basmati 370) at four fertility levels: 60-13.2-0, 60-13.2-24.9, 60-13.2-49.8, and 90-19.8-37.3 kg NPK/ha. Thirty-five-d-old seedlings (2/hill) were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing. All of the P and K was applied before transplanting and the N in two equal splits at 21 and 42 d after transplanting. The grain yield and yield components were recorded at harvesting. Plants were harvested and then dried for 3 d before threshing. Grain yield was recorded at about 16% moisture.

Effect of fertility levels^a on yield and yield components of some scented rices. RRS, India.

^a1 = 60-13.2-0 kg NPK/ha, 2 = 60-13.2-24.9 kg NPK/ha, 3 = 60-13.2-49.8 kg NPK/ha, 4 = 90-19.8-37.3 kg NPK/ha.

Panicles/m² were significantly different among varieties across treatments, with HBC19 having the most. Panicles/m² increased when more fertilizer K was applied in all varieties but their interactive effect was not significant (see figure). Tillers/hill increased with increasing fertility. Spikelet sterility decreased with K application but increased for Basmati 370

as N increased, irrespective of increase in K. Spikelet sterility was drastically reduced in HB1 (see figure).

Grains/panicle increased with increasing NPK levels and was highest in HB1. The 1,000-grain weight of all the varieties increased with increasing K application and the grain yield increased with increasing NPK fertility. By increasing the K application, the yield

increase was highest in HB1, then Basmati 370 and HBC19 (see figure).

Yield increase in the scented rices with K application was because 1,000-grain weight increased, sterility decreased, and the crop did not lodge. Thus, applying K in scented rices is important for producing a good yield. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Green manure: a substitute for inorganic fertilizer N in lowland rice

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Legume green manuring and recycling of crop residues and farmyard manure (FYM) are becoming increasingly important in making today's agriculture sustainable. We studied growing green manure (GM) (*Sesbania rostrata* and *S. aculeata*) during summer fallow and

Table 1. N supplied through GM, FYM, and urea fertilizer to meet the basal requirement of 80 kg N/ha. Pantnagar, India. 1988-91.

Treatment	Proportion of N (kg/ha) applied basally through			
	GM + PU ^a 1988	GM + PU 1989	GM + PU 1990	GM + PU 1991
<i>S. rostrata</i> ^b + prilled urea	60 + 20 (17) ^c	50 + 30 (14)	50 + 30 (14)	60 + 20 (17)
<i>S. aculeata</i> ^d + prilled urea	40 + 40 (10)	60 + 20 (15)	76 + 94 (19)	63 + 17 (16)
FYM ^e + prilled urea	50 + 30 (20)	50 + 30 (20)	50 + 30 (20)	50 + 30 (20)
<i>S. aculeata</i>	60 + 00 (15)	60 + 00 (15)	60 + 00 (15)	47 + 00 (12)
<i>S. aculeata</i>	40 + 00 (11)	53 + 00 (15)	54 + 00 (15)	56 + 00 (16)

^a46% N, ^b1.75% N, 80% moisture. ^c2% N, 80% moisture. ^d0.5% N, 50% moisture. ^eNumbers in parentheses equal the fresh weight of GM and FYM (t/ha).

Table 2. Effects of different GM, FYM, and urea treatments on grain yield of rice. Pantnagar, India. 1988-91.

N source ^a	N rate (kg/ha)	Application method	Grain yield (t/ha)				Mean
			1988	1989	1990	1991	
Control	0	-	3.8	3.9	3.9	2.4	3.5
Urea supergranules	120	Placed at 8-10 cm	5.8	7.7	6.5	7.1	6.8
Prilled urea	120	2/3 N basal and 1/3 N 6-7 d before panicle initiation	5.7	6.8	6.2	5.8	6.1
Prilled urea	90	2/3 N basal and 1/3 N 6-7 d before panicle initiation	5.4	^b	6.9	5.6	5.6
<i>S. rostrata</i> + prilled urea	120	<i>S. rostrata</i> incorporated in situ before transplanting + prilled urea applied in splits	6.1	7.3	6.6	6.8	6.7
<i>S. aculeata</i> + prilled urea	120	<i>S. aculeata</i> incorporated in situ before transplanting + prilled urea applied in splits	6.1	7.6	6.3	6.3	6.6
FYM + prilled urea	120	FYM incorporated 1 mo before transplanting + prilled urea applied in splits	6.1	6.9	6.3	6.9	6.6
<i>S. rostrata</i> (varying, see Table 1)		<i>S. rostrata</i> incorporated in situ	5.2	6.5	6.2	6.7	6.2
<i>S. aculeata</i> (varying, see Table 1)		<i>S. aculeata</i> incorporated in situ	5.2	6.6	6.3	6.0	6.0
Control (extra)			^b	4.4	3.8	2.5	3.6
Control (extra)			3.8	3.8	^b	2.6	3.4
LSD (5%)			0.4	0.5	0.5	0.7	
CV (%)			6	6	6	9	

^aN content in *Sesbania* and FYM was analyzed. After deducting N supplied through these sources, basal N requirement was met using urea. The remaining portion (1/3 of 120 kg N) was applied 6-7 d before panicle initiation. ^b = not tested.